

XX.—*On Dimethyl-Thetine and its Derivatives.* By Professor CRUM BROWN
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(Read 24th November 1873 and 4th May 1874.)

(Sent for Publication 19th August 1878.)

The analogies existing between elements belonging to one "family," such, for instance, as the nitrogen family or the sulphur family, have long been recognised, and are pointed out and insisted upon even in elementary text-books; but the very important analogies existing between substances of different quantivalence are apt to be forgotten or overlooked. For illustrations of such analogies we may point to boron and silicon, elements closely resembling one another in themselves and also in their compounds,—differing, indeed, in little else but that the one is triad and the other tetrad. A similar relation exists between gold and platinum.

The elementary substances, sulphur and phosphorus, have many points of similarity: both fuse at a comparatively low temperature, both are transformed by heat into amorphous insoluble modifications, and both have anomalous vapour densities.

If we turn to their chemical relations and examine the compounds which they form, we find similarities of a very striking kind,—similarities as close as the difference in quantivalence of the two elements will allow.

To illustrate this we have arranged some typical compounds of sulphur and of phosphorus in parallel columns—

P ^{III} .	P ^V .	S ^{II} .	S ^{IV} .	S ^{VI} .
PH ₃ PR ₃	PR ₄ I PR ₄ (OH)	SH ₂ SR ₂	SR ₃ I SR ₃ (OH)	
P ₂ O ₃ P(OH) ₃ or	POH(OH) ₂ PR ₃ O PR ₂ O(OH) PRO(OH) ₂ } P ₂ O ₅ PO(OH) ₃ (PO) ₂ O(OH) ₄		SO ₂ SO(OH) ₂ or SR ₂ O and SRO(OH) and	SO ₂ H(OH) SR ₂ O ₂ SRO ₂ (OH) SO ₃ SO ₂ (OH) ₂ (SO ₂) ₂ O(OH) ₂

This analogy is not confined to the formulæ of the substances; the substances themselves have close resemblances, as any one can see by running the eye over the list given above. It will further be noticed, that in compounds

with hydrogen and electro-positive elements or radicals, triad and pentad phosphorus correspond to dyad and tetrad sulphur respectively, while in compounds with oxygen and electro-negative elements or radicals, triad and pentad phosphorus correspond to tetrad and hexad sulphur respectively.

The following investigation was undertaken with the view of extending the number of comparable compounds by preparing a sulphur compound corresponding to betaine in the nitrogen series, and to the analogous phosphorus compound prepared by HOFMANN.* In this case the term in the nitrogen series exists, and is better known than that in the phosphorus series, so that we may compare our new substance to betaine, although probably it more closely resembles HOFMANN'S phosphorus base.

We have given the substance the name *thetine* to recall its relation to betaine, and the fact that it contains sulphur. The salts of thetine may be regarded as compounds of sulphide of methyl, with substitution products of acetic acid; or as salts of trimethyl-sulphine, in which one atom of hydrogen in one methyl is replaced by carboxyl. Similarly, the salts of betaine may be regarded as compounds of nitride of methyl (trimethylamine), with substitution products of acetic acid, or as salts of tetramethyl-ammonium, in which one atom of hydrogen in one methyl is replaced by carboxyl. If other compounds of this kind are prepared, the nomenclature can easily be adapted to them; thus our base may be called *dimethyl-aceto-thetine*, just as betaine may be called *trimethyl-aceto-betaine*.

These relations are best shown by means of graphic formulæ. Thus—

Hydrombromate of Betaine.

Hydrombromate of Thetine.

Free thetine may be regarded either as—

* HOFMANN, "Proceedings of the Royal Society of London," xi. 525.

or as—

exactly as similar alternative formulæ have been proposed for free betaine.

Hydrobromate of Dimethyl-Thetine.—This substance, from which all the derivatives of dimethyl-thetine are obtained, is produced by the action of sulphide of methyl on bromacetic acid at ordinary temperatures.

For its preparation, sulphide of methyl and bromacetic acid are mixed in a flask connected with a vertical condenser. The flask with condenser attached is then placed in a tub of water, and so arranged that from time to time it may be removed and agitated. Conveniently the tub of water is placed in the corner of a room and the condenser supported by leaning against the angle.

The bromacetic acid rapidly dissolves, but to ensure complete solution the flask should be well shaken, otherwise the thetine compound begins to separate out before the whole of the acid dissolves.

The bromacetic acid is so soluble in sulphide of methyl that the temperature of the mixture sinks below zero, and in one experiment a minimum of -5°C . was observed.

As soon as the whole of the bromacetic acid has dissolved, the mixture begins to grow cloudy, and almost immediately yellowish oily drops begin to separate out; these rapidly increase in quantity, and soon unite to a layer, which eventually forms the greater part of the product. As the oily liquid increases in quantity the temperature of the mixture rises; the action, indeed, is so energetic that unless it be checked by cooling the flask in water, the sulphide of methyl boils off with such violence that even with a long condenser the greater part may be lost. On the termination of the action (which occurs in an hour or two) the product consists of two distinct layers. The lower of these is almost pure dimethyl-thetine hydrobromate; the upper a solution of the thetine compound in sulphide of methyl. The condenser is now removed, the flask loosely corked* and left to itself for a night. Next day the lower oily layer is found to have completely solidified, whilst the upper

* If tightly corked, the flask, unless strong, may burst inwards owing to the absorption which occurs.

layer is almost solid from a network of snow-white needles. The reaction which occurs is represented by the equation—

It should be remarked that, although combination of by far the greater part of the two substances occurs, a certain quantity of each always remains uncombined.*

For the preparation of most of the derivatives of dimethyl-thetine, the crude hydrobromate obtained by the above method is sufficiently pure. But if it be desired to obtain the pure substance, the crude product is best purified by pounding it in a mortar with ether, allowing the mixture to subside, pouring off the supernatant liquid (which contains sulphide of methyl and bromacetic acid), and repeating this process two or three times. The resulting mass of finely powdered thetine compound (which should be quite white) is then rapidly dried between filter paper, and the desiccation completed by placing it over sulphuric acid; or it may be recrystallised from hot alcohol.†

The results of its analysis are as follows:—

	Calculated for $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{SO}_2\text{Br}$.	Obtained.	
Carbon,	23.9	23.7	23.1
Hydrogen,	4.5	4.5	4.8
Oxygen,	51.9	...	...
Sulphur (a),	15.9	...	16.1
Bromine (b),	39.8	40.0	39.7
	100.0		

(a) *Determined as sulphate of baryta after fusion with chlorate and carbonate of potash.*

(b) *Determined as bromide of silver by precipitating the solution of the hydrobromate direct with nitrate of silver.*

Hydrobromate of dimethyl-thetine is a very deliquescent body. It dissolves with ease in hot alcohol, and, if the solution be sufficiently concentrated, crystallises on cooling in large transparent plates, which are apparently rectangular. Large and perfect crystals more than half an inch across and more than an eighth of an inch in thickness are easily grown. It is also soluble,

* See pp. 607–611.

† It should not be boiled too long with alcohol, otherwise it decomposes slowly.

though to a less extent, in sulphide of methyl. It is insoluble in ether. After drying on filter paper the crystals often become brown on the surface; this also occurs with the ethyl compound, and has been noticed with bromacetic acid itself.

Hydrobromate of dimethyl-thetine yields magnificent orange-coloured crystals with chloride of platinum; these are probably isomorphous mixtures of the chloro-platinate and bromo-platinate.

Bromaurate of Dimethyl-Thetine.—This salt was obtained in beautiful, glittering, dark red scales, on mixing alcoholic solutions of bromide of gold and hydrobromate of dimethyl-thetine. It decomposes when heated to 100° C., and also when boiled with alcohol. It was not completely analysed.

Bromo-Platinate of Dimethyl-Thetine was obtained in magnificent dark red crystals, resembling ferricyanide of potassium in appearance, by allowing a solution of hydrobromate of dimethyl-thetine and bromide of platinum to evaporate in a desiccator.

The formula $2(C_4H_9SO_2Br), PtBr_4$ requires 21.3 per cent. of platinum, whereas 21.5 was obtained in two determinations.

Hydrobromate of dimethyl-thetine is completely decomposed by nascent hydrogen, and, as might be expected, yields sulphide of methyl and hydrobromic and acetic acids—

This decomposition occurs when the hydrobromate is treated with zinc and a dilute acid, and also when its aqueous solution is mixed with zinc dust alone—the mixture growing very hot, and sulphide of methyl escaping in abundance.

Hydrobromate of dimethyl-thetine has a pleasant sour taste, and its solution reddens litmus. It acts readily on metallic carbonates, hydrates, and oxides, but the resulting compounds are not necessarily salts simply derived from the hydrobromate by the replacement of the hydrogen of its carboxyl group by metals; but are, in some cases at least, double salts, which may be conveniently represented as compounds of the base dimethyl-thetine with metallic bromides. Of these the most readily prepared is the—

Double Salt of Dimethyl-Thetine and Bromide of Lead.—This salt is produced when an aqueous solution of the hydrobromate is boiled with litharge, carbonate or hydrate of lead, but is most conveniently prepared by means of the latter. The hydrobromate is dissolved in a considerable quantity of water, and recently precipitated hydrate of lead is added. This at once becomes curdy, and, on warming the solution, gradually dissolves. The addition of the

hydrate is continued until the boiling liquid ceases to dissolve it; the solution is then rapidly filtered; as it cools the double salt separates in beautiful silvery scales, which may be purified from mother liquor by washing with a little cold water.

The analysis of this salt shows that it is a compound of 2 molecules of bromide of lead with 1 molecule of dimethyl-thetine—

	Obtained.		Calculated for $\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{SO}_2, 2\text{PbBr}_2.$
Carbon,	5·7	5·7	5·6
Hydrogen,	0·9	0·9	0·9
Bromine,	37·0	37·5	37·0
Lead,	48·4	48·5	48·4

Its formation may be represented by the equation—

That hydrated dimethyl-thetine is produced along with the lead salt was proved by evaporating the mother liquors on a water bath, extracting the residue with alcohol, and adding to the alcoholic solution hydrochloric acid and chloride of platinum, which caused the precipitation of the orange-coloured chloro-platinate of dimethyl-thetine, the composition of which was verified by a platinum determination. The lead salt is very sparingly soluble in cold water, but dissolves to a considerable extent in boiling water, from which it may be recrystallised.

Action of Hydrobromate of Dimethyl-Thetine on Ethylate of Sodium, Oxide of Copper, Oxide of Mercury, and Ammonia.—The action of the hydrobromate on ethylate of sodium appears to vary with the conditions, and has not been thoroughly investigated. In one experiment, on boiling the hydrobromate for some time with ethylate of sodium dissolved in alcohol, the solution almost solidified to a crystalline mass. These crystals were with difficulty soluble in boiling alcohol. An estimation of the sodium which they contained gave 14·6 per cent., whereas the compound $\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{SO}_2, 2\text{NaBr}$ requires 14·4 per cent. A bromine determination gave, however, too small a quantity for the above formula, viz., 36·8 per cent. instead of 49·0. In another experiment, 5 grms. of hydrobromate and 6 grms. of sodium* were separately dissolved in absolute alcohol, and the solutions mixed together, warmed, and filtered. The filtered

* These quantities represent 1 molecule of the hydrobromate and 1 atom of sodium.

liquid grew cloudy and gradually deposited oily drops, which did not crystallise. On evaporating the solution over a water bath a gummy mass was left, which did not invite a closer examination.

Hydrobromate of dimethyl-thetine dissolved in water, and boiled with oxide of copper, yields a beautiful dark blue solution, which becomes of a magnificent purple colour when almost dry. If alcohol be added, purple flakes are precipitated, and alcoholic ammonia produces a magnificent dark blue crystalline precipitate. The blue solution obtained in the first instance when evaporated in vacuo over sulphuric acid gave eventually a purple syrup which would not crystallise.

Alcoholic ammonia digested for a couple of days with the hydrobromate in a sealed tube at 100° C. gave crystals of bromide of ammonium. The solution filtered from these gave a syrupy liquid, which, on evaporation, deposited crystalline matter. This, however, was not examined more closely.

Oxide of mercury, when boiled with the hydrobromate in aqueous solution, is gradually dissolved; oily drops separate, which gradually become crystalline. They consist, in all probability, of a double salt.

That the hydrobromate of dimethyl-thetine behaves as the hydrobromate of a base, and no longer possesses the properties of bromacetic acid, is proved, amongst other of its properties, by the reaction which occurs when its aqueous solution is treated with oxide of silver. The mixture becomes warm, bromide of silver is precipitated, and hydrated dimethyl-thetine remains in solution—

In the case of the action on hydrobromate of dimethyl-thetine of hydrates or oxides of metals, the bromides of which are more or less soluble in water, the bromide first formed combines with the base thetine to form a more or less soluble double salt. In the case, however, of the silver oxide, no such double salt is produced.

Dimethyl-Thetine.—This substance may be obtained either by the action of oxide of silver on the hydrobromate, or by action of carbonate or hydrate of barium on the sulphate of dimethyl-thetine. To prepare it with oxide of silver, a weighed quantity of the hydrobromate is dissolved in water and mixed with rather more than the theoretical quantity of oxide of silver.* The oxide at once becomes yellow, and the mixture grows very hot. It is digested for some

* Conveniently rather more than the equivalent weight of nitrate of silver is converted into oxide by addition of potash solution, and the oxide employed without further weighing. (Equal weights of hydrobromate and nitrate of silver were usually employed.)

The existence of the hemi-hydriodate described further on supports such a view. The dehydration requires eight or nine days for completion.

The loss of water was determined quantitatively, and amounted to 13·1, theory requiring 13·0.

Dimethyl-thetine combines with strong acids such as sulphuric and hydrochloric to form the corresponding sulphate and hydrochlorate; it also combines with hydriodic acid. Most of its salts are, however, more conveniently prepared either from the hydrobromate or sulphate by double decomposition with the corresponding silver or barium salts.

Hydrochlorate of Dimethyl-Thetine.—This salt may be prepared by the action of hydrochloric acid on the base, but more conveniently by the action of chloride of barium on its sulphate.

A weighed quantity of the hydrobromate was dissolved in water and treated with rather more than the equivalent quantity of sulphate of silver. As soon as this ceased to act, the solution was filtered from the bromide of silver, mixed with the equivalent quantity of chloride of barium dissolved in water, the mixture boiled, allowed to settle, and chloride of barium cautiously added till the whole of the sulphuric acid was precipitated. The clear solution was then filtered off and concentrated in vacuo over sulphuric acid, when, after some time, it solidified to a colourless crystalline mass.

Hydrochlorate of dimethyl-thetine is a colourless crystalline substance, having a pleasant sour taste and acid reaction. It is very soluble in water, and is deliquescent. In alcohol it is much less soluble, and may in fact be precipitated by that liquid from its concentrated aqueous solution.

The formula—

was verified by a chlorine determination—

	Calculated in 100.	Obtained.
Chlorine, . . .	22·7	23·3 *

* The excess of chlorine was probably due to a small quantity of hydrochloric acid enclosed within the crystals, as the specimen analysed was obtained from the base and hydrochloric acid.

A further confirmation of the above formula was afforded by the composition of the double salt which the hydrochlorate forms with chloride of platinum.

Chloro-Platinate of Dimethyl-Thetine.—This salt crystallises out in beautiful orange-yellow needles when tolerably concentrated aqueous solutions of the hydrochlorate and chloride of platinum are mixed. It is not very soluble in cold water, but is much more so in boiling water, from which it may be re-crystallised. It is insoluble in alcohol, and when heated with that liquid fuses below its surface, but becomes solid again on cooling.

The salt obtained from aqueous solutions contains 2 molecules of water of crystallisation, and has the formula—

The salt was analysed by determination of water and platinum—

	Calculated in 100.	Obtained.	
Platinum, . . .	28.6	28.5	28.4
Water, . . .	5.2	5.4	...

Hydriodate of Dimethyl-Thetine.—Up to the present time no salt having the composition of the normal hydriodate has been obtained. A solution of the base when warmed with hydriodic acid gradually becomes brown from the separation of free iodine. The same solution, not warmed but allowed to evaporate in vacuo over sulphuric acid, also became brown, and eventually deposited splendid lustrous crystals resembling permanganate of potash in appearance. Attempts to prepare the hydriodate from the sulphate of dimethyl-thetine and iodide of barium were equally unsuccessful, the solution of the hydriodate thus obtained decomposing during evaporation and yielding free iodine.

In another experiment a very concentrated aqueous solution of the base was mixed with exactly the equivalent quantity of recently distilled hydriodic acid of constant boiling point. The mixture was then placed in a desiccator, and after a day or so yielded comparatively colourless crystalline crusts. These were found to contain 34.1 per cent. of iodine. They were recrystallised from a little hot water, and were then found to contain 33.4 per cent. of iodine. A hemi-hydriodate, having the composition expressed by the formula $2(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{SO}_2), \text{HI}$ —*i.e.*, consisting of a compound of 2 molecules of the anhydrous base and 1 molecule of hydriodic acid, requires 34.5 per cent. of iodine—a number closely agreeing with that obtained with the product which had not been recrystallised. Such a salt might be capable of existence thus—

and might decompose when treated with water into hydriodic acid and the hydrated base. The presence of a small quantity of the latter in the recrystallised product would account for the slight deficiency of iodine.

Polyiodide of Dimethyl-Thetine.—The beautiful crystalline salt resembling permanganate of potash in appearance,—which was obtained by the spontaneous decomposition of the hydriodate, or by allowing dilute hydriodic acid to remain for a long time in contact with the base,—is a polyiodide of dimethyl-thetine. It forms well-defined crystals, which are insoluble in water, but soluble in alcohol and ether. Warmed with water they fuse to oily drops, which on cooling do not readily solidify.

The analysis of the salt was effected by dissolving it in alcohol and adding standard hyposulphite solution; as soon as it was decolorised, the total iodine was determined by precipitation as iodide of silver.

The numbers obtained agree with the formula—

	Calculated in 100.	Obtained.		
Free Iodine,	50.6	50.7	50.5	50.4
Total Iodine,	75.9	75.4	...	...

Other polyiodides were obtained by adding iodine to a solution of the base in hydriodic acid. These were beautiful salts with a greenish metallic lustre. As they were probably mixtures, they were not examined more closely.

Sulphate of Dimethyl-Thetine.—This salt is obtained by the action of sulphate of silver on the hydrobromate.

The hydrobromate is dissolved in water, rather more than the equivalent quantity of sulphate of silver added, and the mixture warmed in a water bath and well stirred. From time to time a little of the solution is removed and tested with sulphate of silver, and when this ceases to be affected, the whole is thrown on a filter, and the solution, after removing the small quantity of dissolved sulphate of silver by addition of hydrochloric acid, concentrated either over a water bath or in vacuo over sulphuric acid. When syrupy the solution solidifies to a crystalline mass.

Sulphate of dimethyl-thetine is a colourless crystalline body, and is perhaps the least soluble of all the dimethyl-thetine salts, and is not deliquescent. Nevertheless, its aqueous solution may be concentrated till of syrupy consistence, and frequently remains thus without crystallising. The salt is very slightly soluble in alcohol, and is readily precipitated by that reagent from its concentrated aqueous solution. It has a pleasant sour taste, and its solution reddens litmus paper.

The formula—

was verified by a determination of sulphuric acid—

	Obtained in 100.	Calculated.
SO_4	$\overbrace{28.1 \quad 28.2}$	28.4

Nitrate of Dimethyl-Thetine.—This salt was prepared by the action of nitrate of silver on hydrobromate of dimethyl-thetine. A weighed quantity of the latter was dissolved in water, and a solution containing the equivalent quantity of nitrate of silver added. The mixture was then filtered from the precipitated bromide of silver, and concentrated in vacuo over sulphuric acid. The nitrate separated in large colourless crystals when the solution was of small volume. It has a sour taste, and its solution reddens litmus. It is readily decomposed even when heated at 100°C ., and its aqueous solution when boiled also suffers decomposition, red fumes being given off.

The formula—

was verified by a determination of carbon and hydrogen—

	Calculated in 100.	Obtained
Carbon,	26.2	26.4
Hydrogen,	4.9	4.9